

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 2-8 September 2023
Report published: September 2024

Little and large: surveying and
safeguarding coral reefs & whale
sharks in the Maldives

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Abstract

In September 2023, Biosphere Expeditions ran its 11th annual Reef Check survey expedition to the Maldives. International citizen scientists, supervised by a professional reef biologist, performed Reef Check surveys for one week at North and South Ari atoll at exposed, semi-exposed and sheltered sites. We repeated visits to sites last surveyed in 2018 in this atoll. In the 2018 survey, most of the reefs had not recovered significant coral cover from the 2016 mass coral bleaching event.

Outer reef sites had not changed considerably in their generic coral cover, dominated by *Porites*, *Millepora* and *Pocillopora* corals. Diversity was low, but coral cover was moderate to high (with Bathaalaa, Rasdhoo, and Dhigurah Wall averaging 40% ± 15). The deviation was low at these sites, illustrating the relatively homogeneous nature of outer reef drop off locations (between 5 and 12 m depth).

The two inner reefs differed markedly from each other in response to the bleaching event. Dega thila has become increasingly smothered with corallimorpharians (*Discosoma*) since the first surveys at the site in 2008, and since 2016. Here, before the 2016 bleaching event, the deeper layers of the reef survey (>5 m) were always dominated by these smothering organisms. These had encroached into the shallow (<3 m survey depth) after the bleaching event, leading to shallow water cover of 3.75% that was almost entirely comprised of *Pocillopora damicornis*, rather than the historically dominant *Acropora* table and finger colonies (e.g. *A. humilis* and *A. hyacinthus / clathrata*).

Kudafalhu had recovered to 43% cover since the 2016 bleaching event. There was no visible recovery two years after the 2016 bleaching event at this site when surveyed in 2018, where coral cover was 2% in shallow waters. However, considerable recruitment of branching and table corals had occurred by September 2023. This is the only site we have visited since the 2016 bleaching event that has shown considerable *Acropora* recruitment and growth, making it a reef that should be considered for protected area status.

Fish populations continue to reflect the impact of overfishing on the coral ecosystem. There are low numbers of mid-level carnivores at most sites (snappers and sweetlips), with groupers only occasionally spotted at size >30 cm (fewer than one or two fish on average per transect). We also observed that the important grazing parrotfish were not abundant at reefs, with larger densities frequenting shallow transects.

There were only two crown-of-thorns starfish recorded during the entire expedition, both at Bathaalaa Maagaa. There was little coral disease, but a high prevalence of *Drupella* corallivorous snail outbreaks at offshore sites, with approximately 40 living colonies affected at Bathaalaa Maagaa alone.

Rare and charismatic animals sighted included nurse sharks (Baros training site), a large school of glasseye *Heteropriacanthus cruentatus* at Dega Thila (over 300 individuals), reef octopus, hawksbill turtle, blacktip and white-tip sharks, and an eagle ray at Rasdhoo. Three bumphead parrotfish and a white-tip shark were seen off-transect at Bathaalaa Maagaa. In addition, a dogtooth tuna was recorded. A hawksbill turtle was recorded off transect at Kudafalhu. A napoleon wrasse, triton shell and hawksbill turtle were recorded at Dhigurah. A banded coral shrimp was recorded at Bathaalaa Maagaa.

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1. Expedition review

1.1. Background

Background information, location, conditions and the general research area are as described in [Solandt & Hammer \(2019\)](#).

1.2. Dates & team

The 2023 annual Reef Check survey ran over a week from 2 to 8 September 2023 with a team of international citizen scientists, a professional scientist, and an expedition leader.

The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities, and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence): Jenan Alasfoor (Oman), Avantika Chaturvedi (India), Jennifer Fox (UK), Robert Fox (UK), Tania Kacamer (UK), Dr. Kristine Klatt (Germany), Katharina Koll (Switzerland), Mansoureh Mazraifarhani (UK), Ruth Morlas (USA), Ezekiel Richardson (USA), Nils Uhlenbrock (Germany), Jessica Zins (Germany).

Figure 1.2a. Expedition team and boat staff (in orange T-shirts) 2023.

The expedition scientist was Dr. Jean-Luc Solandt, a Londoner with a degree in Marine Biology from the University of Liverpool. After graduating, he spent a year working on the Great Barrier Reef assisting field scientists in studies on fisheries, and the ecology of soft corals and damselfish. He returned to the UK and enrolled in a Ph.D. in sea urchin ecology in Jamaica, based both in London and Jamaica. He went on to be an expedition science co-ordinator for projects in Tanzania, the Philippines and Fiji, and has successfully undertaken campaign, science and policy work in planning and managing Marine Protected Areas in the UK and western Europe since 2008. He has been the Reef Check co-ordinator for the Maldives since 2005, and has thus far led 11 expeditions to the islands. Jean-Luc has over 1100 dives clocked up since he first trained to be a marine biologist 32 years ago.

The expedition was led by Dr. Matthias Hammer, who founded Biosphere Expeditions in 1999. Born in Germany, he went to school there, before joining the Army, and serving for several years amongst other units with the German Parachute Regiment. After active service he came to the UK and was educated at St Andrews, Oxford and Cambridge. During his time at university he either organised or was involved in the running of several expeditions, some of which were conservation expeditions (for example to the Brazilian Amazon and Madagascar), whilst others were mountaineering/climbing expeditions (for example to the Russian Caucasus, the Alps or the Rocky Mountains). With Biosphere Expeditions he has led teams all over the globe. He is a qualified wilderness medical officer, ski instructor, mountain leader, divemaster and survival skills instructor. Once a rower on the international circuit, he is now an amateur marathon runner and Ironman triathlete.

Jenan Alasfoor and Dr. Kristine Klatt supported the teaching and training effort in their roles as Reef Check trainers.

1.3. Partners

On this project Biosphere Expeditions worked with Reef Check, 'Save the Beach' Maldives, the Marine Conservation Society, the Maldives Marine Research Centre (MRC) of the Ministry of Fisheries and Agriculture, Maldives Whale Shark Research Programme (MWSRP), Land and Marine Environmental Resource (LaMer) Group and the MV Theia liveboard.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions, which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as citizen scientists, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Thank you to all of you and the ones we have not managed to mention by name (you know who you are) for making it all happen. Thank you to the crew of [MV Theia](#), our liveboard expedition base, for being such excellent and capable hosts. Thank you also to Hussein Zahir of LaMer for guidance and advice, and Hassan Beybe and Farish Mohammed for welcoming expedition participants to Vilingili Island to discuss the work and infrastructure of 'Save the Beach' Maldives. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support. We also thank the IUCN who have collaborated with us over recent months to produce a paper on bleaching resilience (Cowburn et al. 2019).

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

A multimedia expedition diary is available on <https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/maldives-2023/>.

This and all other expedition reports of this and all other expeditions are available on <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

1.6. Expedition budget

Each participating citizen scientist paid towards expedition costs a contribution of €2,880 per seven-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, all maps and special non-personal equipment, all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs, etc., as well as visas and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how these contributions were spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	23,238
Expenditure	
Staff includes local & international salaries, travel, and expenses	4,360
Research includes equipment and other research expenses	68
Transport includes taxis and other local transport	0
Base includes board, lodging and other live-aboard services	25,516
Administration includes some admin and miscellaneous costs	55
Team recruitment Maldives as estimated % of PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	7,334
Income – Expenditure	-14,095
Total percentage spent directly on project	161%*

*This means that in 2023, the expedition ran at a loss and was supported over and above the income from the expedition contributions and grants by Biosphere Expeditions.

2. Reef Check survey

2.1. Introduction and background

Review up to 2023

A review of the rationale for the expedition and the situation of the Maldives up to 2019 is described in Solandt & Hammer (2020). This includes sub-chapters on Maldivian coral reefs, fisheries, coral bleaching, previous Reef Check surveys, descriptions of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs), governance and management, as well as the 1998 and 2015/2016 bleaching events.

After nine annual expeditions in 2011-2019 (all expedition reports [here](#)), there were no expeditions in 2020 and 2021 because of the COVID-19 pandemic. There were no significant bleaching events in the Maldives recorded during this two-year gap. There was a minor bleaching event in June 2020, but online forums suggest that this did not affect populations of corals in the Maldives significantly. Expeditions in 2019 and 2022 were in South Male' and Vaavu atolls, partly to monitor new reef locations, and partly due to a lack of recovery of the North and South Ari atoll reefs in 2018. In 2023, we changed our expedition location to the original survey sites from North Ari, to see if there had been significant changes in coral cover, lifeforms, and patterns seven years after the 2016 bleaching event (Solandt and Hammer 2019). At the last time of visiting these sites, the inner reefs (Dega Thilla and Kudafalhu) were particularly badly affected by bleaching from the 2016 event.

There is no change to the summary of threats to Maldives reefs, both on the local anthropogenic and global climate-induced level. Key threats are:

- Climate change and associated sea surface temperature increases leading to coral bleaching (from human-caused increases in CO₂ concentration)
- Increased atmospheric CO₂ concentration that results in seawater acidification; this leads to decreased skeletal strength of calcium carbonate-dependent corals, decreased growth rate, and decreased reproductive output of corals
- Overfishing of keystone species (e.g. predators of Crown-of-Thorns and herbivorous fish)
- Sedimentation and inappropriate/unsustainable atoll development
- Poor water treatment
- Solid waste

The Maldives have semi-autonomous atoll councils that have some powers of local decision-making, particularly with regard to reef fishing. As a result, some of the recommendations from past reports have been met with resistance. The provision to increase the minimum landing sizes for some species into the grouper cages and for market is one example. Given the small sizes of many species seen in the wild, as outlined in previous reports (Solandt and Hammer 2015, 2017a, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2023, Solandt et al. 2016), it is regrettable that the trajectory for the Maldives over-fishing of reef species affects revenues and the natural population.

A [Blue Marine Foundation](#) project works in the south, with resort partners and the government, to reform fisheries management at Laamu atoll¹. Blue Marine Foundation research from Laamu has shown that fish resources are now being exploited by heavier lined 'jig' fishing at the outside of reefs. This is leading to a greater exploitation of new stocks at, or around, 100m depth, as the shallow reef fish populations are now denuded. Further survey work at Laamu has involved social science and resource use discussions with resort and local islands. There is an attempt in Laamu to get local atoll councils involved in delivering fisheries management measures, particularly with resorts. It is essential that all resorts within the atoll sign up to sustainable fisheries management so that local fishers and resorts can act together to develop long-term reduction in fishing pressure.

Due to past political interference in the rule of law and due process, there were several developments that were patently counterproductive to the Maldives environment under the previous governments. Profit-driven resort development, and other major capital infrastructure project investments from overseas, were permitted despite environmental concerns raised by The Environment Protection Agency (EPA) and MRC. Decisions by the EPA were effectively rejected by the tourism ministry². Interestingly, this is not necessarily that different in western democracies, where there is an inability of citizens to challenge decisions in court due to prohibitive expense.

2.2. Methods and planning

Biosphere Expeditions uses the [Reef Check methodology](#) for its coral reef surveys (see Solandt and Hammer 2015, 2017a, 2018, 2019, Solandt et al. 2016 and earlier reports on www.biosphere-expeditions.org/reports for details). The 2023 surveys were carried out with the aim of recording patterns of recovery and resilience from the 2016 bleaching in North and South Ari Atolls.

We surveyed five sites (see Table 2.3a) to repeat surveys carried out in 2018 (Solandt and Hammer 2019) and going back to 2011. Training was conducted at reefs to the west of Baros House reef. We then trained and surveyed at sites of steep forereef walls (e.g. Rasdhoo and Dhigurah Wall), sheltered inner reef (Kudafalhu and Dega Thilla) and sloping outer reefs in semi-exposed locations (e.g. Bathaalaa Maagaa). One site could not be surveyed because of the strength of currents (Holiday Thila). Shallow dives were between 3 and 4 m, with deeper divers from 7 to 9 m.

All training was completed on board the MV Theia during the first three days of the expedition. Biosphere Expeditions recruited citizen scientists, carried out logistics, and provided health and safety on board the research vessel. The scientific programme, training, data collection, and analysis was led by Dr Jean-Luc Solandt (Reef Check Course Director) and supported by Dr Matthias Hammer (Reef Check Course Director) as well as Reef Check Trainers Jenan Alasfoor and Dr. Kristine Klatt.

¹ <http://www.blumarinefoundation.com/project/maldives/>

² <http://www.climatechangenews.com/2017/03/20/maldives-regime-imperils-coral-reefs-dash-cash/>

2.3. Results

Sites surveyed

[Sites surveyed during the 2023 expedition](#) were a mixture of inner atoll sites (thilas and girls) and outer reef slopes. Sites (Table 2.3a and Figure 2.3a) were surveyed based on accessibility to Male' during week-long live-aboard expeditions, exposure, a mix of inner and outer reefs, and because they demonstrated a typical range of Maldivian reefs.

Table 2.3a. Site names and locations. See also [online map](#) and Figure 2.3a below.

Site name	Date	Latitude	Longitude	Inner / outer reef	Atoll
Baros*	2.9.23	4.287 N	73.4215 E	Inner	South Male'
Rasdhoov Madivaruvu	4.9.23	4.2655 N	73.0016 E	Outer	North Ari
Bathaalaa Maagaa	5.9.23	4.0558 N	72.9564 E	Outer	North Ari
Kudafalhu	5.9.23	4.0168 N	7.8057 E	Inner	North Ari
Dega Thila	6.9.23	3.8448 N	72.7511 E	Inner	South Ari
Holiday Thila**	6.9.23	3.4946 N	72.8227 E	Inner	South Ari
Dhigurah Wall	7.9.23	3.5160 N	72.9184 E	Outer	South Ari

*Check site (for safety and equipment checks) & training site.

**Not surveyed due to excess currents (safety considerations).

Figure 2.3a. Central Maldives atolls with survey locations (see also [online map](#)).

Coral cover

Hard coral (HC) cover ranged from 4% (Dega Thila) to 64% (Bathaalaa Maagaa) (Figure 2.3b) from all sites and depths.

Figure 2.3b. Mean benthic cover (+SD) at 3-4 m (shallow) and 7-10 m (deep) at 5 sites surveyed in 2023. HC – Hard Coral; SC – Soft Coral; RKC – Recently Killed Coral; NIA – Nutrient Indicator Algae; SP – Sponge; RC – Rock; RB – Rubble; SD – Sand; SI – Silt; OT – Other. Other is largely *Discosoma* and principally from Dega Thila.

The sites with the greatest change in coral cover since the 2018 surveys were Kudafalhu and Dega Thila. At Kudafalhu there was 1% coral cover in the shallow transect in 2018, with the reef dominated by thick algal turf (NIA) and dead coral rock. This site has had a considerable recruitment of *Acropora* corals since then, increasing the shallow water coral growth to 43%. The deeper transect had coral cover of 8%, indicating that recruitment and growth was in the shallower areas.

Dega Thila has had further incursion and dominance of Corralimorph *Discosoma* over the dead coral framework since 2018. This dominates to such an extent that any recruitment of corals is unlikely. The only live coral colonies were of *Pocillopora eydouxi* or *damicornis*.

Comparing sites over time before and after bleaching (2016)

At Dega we have seen a persistent decline in coral cover over twelve years of surveys, with Corallimorpharian (OT) cover increasing exponentially since 2011, and particularly after the 2016 bleaching event. However, we see a pattern of no real significant change at Bathaalaa Maagaa and Rasdhoo Madivaru. Kudafalhu has seen a great decline in coral cover, followed by an increase, with significant recruitment of *Acropora* since 2018.

Rasdhoo Madivaru (outer reef) has shown **resilience** to bleaching stress, with a limited change in coral cover (Figure 2.3c). Before the 2016 bleaching event, it had a mean of 41% HC at 5 m depth (mean from 2008, 2011, 2015). This reduced to 34% two months after the 2016 bleaching event. Coral cover then recovered quickly to 45% (2018 and 2023 surveys). This trend was also replicated by Dhigurah and Bathaalaa sites that showed similar outer reef resilience.

Dega Thila (inner reef) showed a **phase-shift** trend with a moderate shallow water coral cover of 42% (2008, 2011), followed by 16% HC cover two months after the 2016 bleaching event (Figure 2.3c). This cover became very low (2018, 2023), at an average of 4.67% after 2016. The remaining dead *Acropora* framework of table corals was replaced by an increased dominance of *Discosoma* corallimorphs (OT category). This dominant species has almost completely covered the entire structure of the southern Thila. *Discosoma* increased from 38% cover in 2008 and 2011, to 41% two months after the 2016 bleaching event, before reaching an average of 71% in 2018 and 2023. This showed a phase-shift from a balanced coral-corallimorph dominated site to one dominated by corallimorpharians, with almost complete absence of *Acropora* that had been dominant in 2011. *Pocillopora* was the only significant coral genera present during the 2023 survey, indicating that not only had the benthic habitat changed, but that the only genus tolerant to *Discosoma* is *Pocillopora* spp.

The third inner reef site with long-term monitoring (Kadafalhu in the centre of North Ari Atoll) showed a **recovery** trend. This site, first visited in 2011, had excellent shallow-water *Acropora* assemblages. Mean HC cover at 3 m depth was 67% for 2011, 2013, and 2015 (combined data for all years), prior to bleaching in 2016. A couple of years after the bleaching (2017 and 2018), the HC cover was reduced to 2%. Surveys in 2023 at exactly the same depth and site showed that HC cover had reached 43%.

Rasdho Madivaru

2016

2023

Dega Thila

2016

2023

Kudafhalu

2016

2023

Figure 2.3c. Change in substrate (hard coral and other – *Discosoma* corallimorphs) at three long-term monitoring sites from North Ari atoll.

Rasdho Madivaru shows limited hard coral cover change at shallow reefcrest depth at 5 m (left), both before, during, and after bleaching events. Note the partially bleached *Porites* colony to the bottom right of the 2016 image, indicating continued recovery from the bleaching event.

Dega Thila (middle) shows increased encroachment and dominance of corallimorphs at the shallow transect area after 2016 bleaching (2-3 m depth).

Kudafhalu (right) by contrast shows recruitment and recovery of *Acropora* coral cover at the shallow transect location after 2016 (2-3 m depth).

Figure 2.3d. Coral reef at 12-5 m at Baros. Note that the coral colonies are rather small. *Acropora* (bottom left, centre left) are largely rare. *Pocillopora* (top left) is reasonably common throughout the Maldives. *Pavona clavus* (top right) is fairly rare. *Diploastrea* (right centre), *Pachyseris* spp. are also uncommon.

Figure 2.3e. Shallow water (2 m) Dega Thila dead *Acropora* spp. coral framework and some living *Pocillopora* spp. (4% live coral cover) covered with *Discosoma* corallimorpharians in 2023 (top). Corallimorph encroachment from deeper waters into this zone has happened since the 2016 bleaching event. Bottom image is of the same site in 2011.

Figure 2.3f. Dhigurah Wall at 6m from the deep forereef slope looking north into shallow waters. This is a typical exposed forereef crest, subject to large swells, particularly from the southwest. This leads to relatively low coral cover at this exposed depth. Live hard coral cover was 28% at this depth (largely *Pocillopora* and *Porites*).

Fish populations

Bleaching episodes in the past have caused a loss of diversity and complexity of the three-dimensional habitat (Jones et al. 2004). Previous research conducted after the 1998 global bleaching event found that the loss of habitat had a considerable impact on the diversity and abundance of many reef fish species and families (Pratchett et al. 2011). It is therefore important to monitor the diversity and abundance of fish present on reefs to determine the effects of such disturbance events on the wider marine community.

Fish were also recorded from all sites from a number of different families and species. Butterflyfish, snapper, sweetlip (*Haemulidae*) and parrotfish were recorded at most sites. Fish populations were greater in numbers in shallow waters and represented by the butterflyfish family.

Figure 2.3g-1. Fish populations (per 500 m³ replicate) from all sites surveyed in 2022 at shallow transects. Parrotfish are only recorded over 20 cm.

Figure 2.3g-2. Fish populations (per 500 m³ replicate) from all sites surveyed in 2022 at deep transects. Parrotfish are only recorded over 20 cm.

Butterflyfish, snapper and parrotfish numbers were particularly increased at shallow Kudafalhu in 2023 compared to 2018 (when the fish was at particularly low density) (Table 2.3b). Between 2018 and 2023, the coral cover has increased at this site and depth from 2% to 43%. *Acropora* is correlative with increased densities of butterflyfish species, both as prey (some butterflyfish eat the polyps of live corals), and as sheltering habitat (Pratchett *et al.*, 2011 & 2014). There was an 8-fold increase in parrotfish numbers on the shallow reef in 2023 compared to 2018, again indicative of healthier reef conditions at this depth. There was a smaller (2-fold) increase in parrotfish at the deeper transect than at the shallow transect, that could be because the habitat at this greater depth hadn't had a significant increase in coral cover and the benthos was covered in large part by dead coral rubble and sand (over 80% of the benthos). These aren't suitable feeding habitats for scarids, that utilise the algal turf growth on dead coral framework (Wolfe *et al.*, 2021). This is because the small rubble at Kudafalhu is constantly moved from shallow to deeper waters (as it lies on a 30 degree slope at 7m). It has a high level of sandy sediment concentration around the rubble (that is predominantly of dead branching corals). There is also less shelter in the deep transect, that would make these fish more vulnerable to predation from predators. Also, some parrotfish species in the Maldives are corallivorous, that would lead to greater abundance in shallow reefs (Shantz and Ladd, 2024).

Table 2.3b. Change in fish population at Kudafalhu at different coral states. In 2023, the coral cover was at 25% for both depths combined (43% at shallow transect and 8% at deep transect), and in 2018, at 2% (1% at shallow transect and 3% at deep transect).

Fish family /	2018		2023	
	Shallow (2.5 m)	Deep (7 m)	Shallow (2 m)	Deep (7 m)
Butterflyfish	3.25	6.5	32.75	2.75
Haemulidae	0	0	1.5	0
Snapper	20	16	28.25	11.25
Parrotfish	0.5	0.75	4	1.5
Moray eel	0	0	0	0
Grouper (all)	0	0	0.5	0
LIVE HC cover (%)	1	3	43	8

Figure 2.3h. Typical images of shallow Kudafalhu at 2023 (left) at 43% living coral cover relative to 2018 (right) at 2% living coral cover at 2.5m.

Figure 2.3i. A nurse shark sheltering in a coral head at the training site (Baros).

Unusual sightings

Reef Check records megafauna off-transect (sharks, turtles, rays, cetaceans). Surveyors also reported bumphead parrotfish and napoleon wrasse off-transect. Unusual and notable observations of large numbers of species were also recorded such as giant clams and triton's trumpet – a very rare occurrence for Reef Check surveys, with only one other such shell recorded on a leisure dive, during a snorkel on a resort house reef in 2012.

Table 2.3c. Unusual sightings at the five reef check sites. Note the greater numbers of large fish sightings at offshore and outer reef sites (Rasdho Madivaru, Bathaalaa Maagaa and Dhigurah Wall).

	Rasdho Madivaru	Bathaalaa Maagaa	Kudafalhu	Dega Thilla	Dhigurah Wall
Sharks	3 white-tip, 1 black-tip	1 white-tip			
Turtles	Hawksbill	Hawksbill	Hawksbill		Hawksbill
Rays	Eagle ray				
Fish		Dogtooth tuna; 3 bumphead parrotfish (off transect)		Large school of glasseye (<i>H. cruentatus</i>).	Napoleon wrasse off (deep) transect.
Other	Reef octopus	50 giant clams recorded over the entire 100m transect	27 giant clams recorded along the entire transect		23 giant clams. 1 triton's trumpet shell recorded on the deep transect.

Figure 2.3j. A school of glasseye (*Heteropriacanthus cruentatus*) at Dega Thila.

Invertebrate populations

An important mobile invertebrate recorded on Maldives Reef Check dives is the corallivorous snail *Drupella*. It was found at all sites, with significant impacts at Bathaalaa Maagaa and Rasdhoo Madivaru, as 14 colonies and 20 colonies were affected by infestations, at shallow and deep transects, respectively. *Drupella* was also recorded at Kudafalhu. Although not part of the official RC survey, we train surveyors on how to identify animals based on feeding scars, and individual animals, and record the numbers of colonies affected (not individual *Drupella* animals). This gives us a record of living coral colonies (typically *Acropora* genera) that are typically affected by these predators.

A single Crown-of-Thorns starfish was reported from Bathaalaa Maagaa.

Giant clams were common, particularly at Bathaalaa Maagaa with 50 individuals recorded along the entire transect. There were also 27 recorded at Kudafalhu.

Sea cucumbers were common with recordings of *Stichopus chloronotus* being most common at Bathaalaa Maagaa.

A single banded coral shrimp *Stenopus hispidus* was recorded at Bathaalaa Maagaa.

The most damaging and pervasive species that is creating a habitat is the corallimorpharian, *Discosoma* sp. that had further colonised the shallow transect at Dega Thila (Figure 2.3e). This smothering animal was only at the deeper transect in 2018 at significant densities.

There was low impact from bleaching and disease. There was only one unverified observation of white-band disease from Bathaalaa Maagaa.

Whale shark sightings

No effort-based whale shark surveys took place in this expedition due to time constraints and inclement weather.

2.4. Discussion and outlook

Coral reef resilience, recovery and phase-shifts

Cowburn et al. (2019) discussed the issue of environmental conditions leading to coral reef resilience in the Maldives. This study indicated from Current/Temperature/Depth loggers at Rasdhoo Madivaru that the shallow nature of the site adjacent to deep water, the potential for upwellings, and being close to a reef channel (the cut between the inner and outer reef down to at least 20 m) allows for considerable water exchange in volume and temperature. This is markedly different from the inner reefs of the Maldives, particularly those lying deep within atolls, that are more likely to be affected by increased water temperature, and that has more stagnant water between tides (Solandt and Hammer 2017).

There is some evidence of thermal adaptation of coral reefs, depending on taxa, colony size, depth, and other characteristics: Branching corals survive better at increased depth and at smaller size guilds, according to studies in French Polynesia (Winslow et al. 2024). There are examples from other Indo-Pacific regions of *P. lobata* (the dominant forereef massive reef-building coral species on Maldives outer reefs) being more resilient at exposed outer-reef locations to bleaching events (e.g. Morais et al. 2024, Morais et al. 2021, Cowburn et al. 2019): They are not as likely to bleach in the first place and individual colonies can recover once bleached. They may partially bleach, leading to patches of whitening within colonies, that subsequently recover their zooxanthellae. This is rarer in the species more susceptible to bleaching such as *Acropora hyacinthus* and *clathrata* – table coral species that can be abundant on more sheltered reef crests. There is a mechanical advantage in the size and robust growth form of massive *Porites* corals: They are more resistant to storm damage due to their ‘massive’ growth form. In addition, *Porites* abundance on Maldivian reef crests adjacent to the deep water provides them with regular passage of cooler water (at least twice a day) into the coral atoll, where the reefs are near to channels during flood tides (e.g. at Rasdhoo).

Over the past ten years, some of the inner reef sites that we have observed at Ari atoll have progressed through a ‘phase shift’ (as noted by Hughes 1994), from coral reefs to algal, sponge, and corallimorph dominated seabed biotopes. A ‘phase shift’ occurred in Jamaica and over much of the Caribbean in the early 1990s (Knowlton and Jackson 2008) due to a loss of herbivores as a result of chronic overfishing (of parrotfish) and disease (of *Diadema* urchin). Coupled with land-based nutrient input and catastrophic impact from hurricanes that destroyed the living coral framework, the Jamaican marine environment shifted from a coral-dominated state to an algal-dominated state within three years in the late 1980s (personal observation). This shift now also appears to be occurring on some inner atoll reefs of the Maldives. When reefs are free of herbivory (largely due to overfishing of parrotfish and surgeonfish), the remaining fish and invertebrate populations are not adapted to consume the species of algae that start to dominate affected reefs (e.g. *Dictyota*, *Padina*, *Tydemania*, *Halimeda*). Some larger, more complex algae (e.g. *Sargassum* sp. and *Padina* sp.) are leathery and/or defended from herbivores by toxic secondary metabolites and/or calcification of tissues. At the Great Barrier Reef, for example, certain acanthurid species (surgeonfish, tangs and unicornfish) preferentially feed on small *Sargassum* plants, whilst chubs (Kyphosidae) preferentially fed on larger plants (Hoey 2010). *Padina* sp. was particularly dominant at Thelueligaa inner reef (Ari atoll) that was severely affected by bleaching in 2016. This reef had already experienced a ‘phase shift’ from coral to macroalgal dominance when surveyed in July 2018 (Solandt and Hammer 2019). This is why it is essential that natural food webs are maintained in reef systems.

This shift to non-coral dominance was recorded at Dega Thila, which historically (when initially surveyed in 2011) had 67% coral cover at 2-3 m depths, with similar cover up until 2015. The deeper transect depth (at 7 m) was dominated by corallimorphs during the entire period of our surveys (since 2011). The *Discosoma* assemblages now appear to have taken over the habitat above 3 m depth, encroaching throughout the coral framework. This phase-shift from a coral to ‘other’ dominant characteristic species or habitat has now reached an alternative ‘stable state’ (Knowlton 1992). This new ‘stable state’ is maintained by self-reinforcing feedback mechanisms (Nystrom et al. 2008), such as asexual reproduction from existing corallimorphs. Similar phase shifts from coral to corallimorph-dominated reefs has been witnessed in Palmyra and other Indo-Pacific nations and oceanic atolls (Kelly et al.

2012, Norstrom et al. 2009, Work et al. 2008, Rajasuriya & Karunarathna, 2000) that have been linked to increased iron release from sunken vessels. Iron is a nutrient that supports plankton and other lifeforms to grow in otherwise relatively oligotrophic conditions. Such input can lead to increased beneficial conditions for corallimorpharians (Work et al 2008). Loya (2004) reported corallimorph dominance on reefs after an extreme low-tide event in a Red Sea reef. After coral mortality, corallimorphs dominated the subsequent recruitment and shallow reef that was not stimulated by excess iron in the water. At Dega Thila, the stress threshold state of *Acropora* shallow-water dominance was shifted to corallimorph dominance induced by the bleaching induced mortality of the living reef in 2016, and the presence of the deeper water population of these lifeforms. As the current state and lack of predators of corallimorphs is naturally very low on reefs, it is unlikely that there will be a shift/return to a coral-dominated state of this reef (Norstrom et al., 2009; Knowlton, 1992).

Recovery of a reef has been observed at Kudafalhu. This site was badly affected by the 2016 bleaching, with almost 100% loss of the living coral cover down to 2%. This site was not surveyed between 2018 and 2023, because it was approaching a new non-hard coral dominated state (algal turf covered). However, surveying the site in September 2023 showed a strong recovery of *Acropora* in the shallow transect; an increase to 43% cover.

Some reefs at the Great Barrier Reef have been described as ‘sentinel’ reefs (Ani et al. 2024), in that they are resilient to bleaching, and as a system can recover back to a coral-dominated state. This ‘resilience’ is different from ‘resistant’, which is more the nature of *P. lobata* dominated outer/oceanic reef crests, where the reefs may partially bleach but quickly recover their zooxanthellae. The nature of the recovery back to a coral-dominated site is encouraging at Kudafalhu, suggesting good water quality, herbivore biomass and control, and a nearby (larval) source reef. Conditions were likely to have been conducive to recruitment after the 2018 survey, which was not anticipated (no recruits were observed).

The shallow reef crests of Kudafalhu and Dega Thila were similar in 2016, with encrusting coralline algae and turf algae present, but it seems they then followed different ecological trajectories, with Kudafalhu recovering and Dega Thila at a new corallimorph-dominated stable state that is unlikely to return to a coral-dominated state.

Outlook

We are living in unprecedented times, with climate breakdown locked in for at least the next 20+ years (Sully et al. 2019, Brown and Caldera 2017). If we were to reduce CO₂ emissions today to below 350 ppm (the level at which most scientists believe we will reduce global temperatures), we will still have a lag-phase from the CO₂ that remains in the atmosphere and to be released from the planet’s ongoing use of fossil fuels (Zickfeld and Herrington 2015). Consequently, the impact of climate breakdown will continue to be multifarious and overwhelmingly negative to human existence, threatening the continuation of human civilisation as we know it today. The central Maldives can serve as a particularly stark example with very worrying trends emerging. These involve long-term and short-term impacts making a lasting impression on the coral assemblages, fish populations (Sattar et al. 2012, Richardson et al. 2018), and the general health of the marine life surrounding the islands. This includes increasing incidences of disease (Montano et al. 2015), Crown of Thorns (Saponari et al. 2014), *Drupella* predation, and corallimorph outbreaks (Norstrom et al. 2009)).

These trends are not new and have been observed since the mid to late 1990s, coinciding with greater development of the islands, increased fishing pressure to meet the demands of the resort industry, and ever-shortening periods between coral bleaching events (1998, 2016, 2020 and 2024).

The decline of Maldives reefs was set in motion in the 1990s by four principal factors: (1) the first mass-bleaching event in 1998 triggered by El Niño, ocean acidification, and overall increased sea surface temperature (caused by climate change); (2) the development of commercial fisheries for the live-fish trade (principally targeting grouper) and demand for reef-fish; (3) the large-scale expansion of the tourism infrastructure; and (4) the inaction of recent governments to balance economic growth with societal and environmental stability.

Added to this is the recent island expansion programme that has locked the Maldives into debt to foreign investors for generations^{3 4}, whilst at the same time reducing or destroying environmental natural capital (seagrass beds, fish stocks, and coral reefs)^{5 6}.

The industrialisation of the Maldives has had associated costs. Many Maldivians would argue that the tourism and fisheries sectors have helped to provide jobs for Maldivian citizens. This is undoubtedly true, but at what cost? Immediate concerns over climate-driven sea-level rise were recently addressed by the policies and actions of former President Mohammed Nasheed (in office 2008 – 2012). His administration was concerned over climate predictions resulting in sea level rise and increased storms that have already inundated parts of the country. Climate models predict that most of the Maldives islands will be underwater within 50 years (e.g. Viner and Agnew 2000⁷).

A 'green tax' has been levied on tourists since October 2016⁸. The tax is \$6 per night at all-inclusive resorts, and \$3 per night at guest houses on local islands. The Maldives collected over \$30 million in the first half of 2019⁹ from this resource. Projects that create tangible 'capital' outputs, such as water and sewage, as well as waste management plants and the associated infrastructure are needed. Whilst these examples are a progressive use of the green fund achieving societal interest, there is no process for public or civil society to tap into green tax funds, nor are there projects or programmes to track marine environmental quality and trends for improving adaptive management and environmental governance. As such, environmental groups in the Maldives often seek external donor money to undertake monitoring, research, to help protect MPAs, enhance fish populations, and to establish the best conditions to promote coral recovery. A good further use of public funds would be to protect the numerous MPAs from illegal fishing activity that has been successful in other countries, and at the only adequately protected Maldivian MPA –

³ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-maldives-election-debt-idUSKCN1LY1QR>

⁴ <https://www.tourism-watch.de/en/article/maldives-island-state-in-debt/>

⁵ <https://theconversation.com/the-maldives-is-threatened-by-rising-seas-but-coastal-development-is-causing-even-more-pressing-environmental-issues-170144>

⁶ <https://www.climatechangenews.com/2022/03/25/maldives-greenlights-destructive-dredging-to-build-housing-and-luxury-resorts/>

⁷ <https://crudata.uea.ac.uk/cru/posters/2000-11-DV-tourism.pdf>

⁸ <https://www.mira.gov.mv/Pages/View/whatisgreentax>

⁹ <https://greenfiscalspolicy.org/the-maldives-collects-nearly-30m-as-green-tax-in-six-months/>

Hanifaru Bay. This results in the MPA recovery work being neglected, a problem that also occurs in the other countries, including the UK, where there are 350 MPAs, only a small proportion of which are adequately managed. One issue common to all countries is that politicians want results within their term of government. This time frame is typically too short for the 5+ years that may be needed for MPAs to show their effectiveness. Therefore, investment in environmental projects is difficult to come by.

In the Maldives, there has been a push to increase tourist numbers since 2015. In 2018, visitor numbers increased to 1,403,000 (from 1,088,000 in 2014¹⁰). The total number of resorts now stands at over 171¹¹, with more than 520 guest houses being developed on local islands as an increasing share of the tourism market (the author stayed at the local island 'Fulidhoo' during the training of the Fulidhoo dive centre staff in Maldives RC methods in 2019). The Maldives has been proactive in developing new markets in the face of more traditional tourism markets from Europe declining. However, investment in tourism has not been matched by environmental precaution or the "polluter pays" principle that is within UK and EU laws. This principle intends to stave off the worst impacts of capital growth on the environment (in UK there is the Environment Act that calls for Environmental 'Net Gain' whereby development projects need to be offset by nearby environmental enhancement and restoration efforts). Proper financial accounting of healthy marine ecosystems¹² would help to showcase the importance of nature for the country's wellbeing¹³.

The political changes in the Maldives over the past 15 years¹⁴, along with increased national debt from major internationally funded capital projects, have led to increased land and island reclamation for island creation. This aims to make space for indigenous populations, capital infrastructure, but also tourism expansion. Combined with other environmental issues, these major capital projects move environmental degradation beyond sustainable limits for essential coral protection and natural resource management (at least for central atoll reefs where we regularly survey). Construction has an attractive short-term positive impact on the country's Gross Domestic Product, and is politically attractive, but the impacts on the wider ecosystem and population are not effectively accounted for. Many of the islands of the Maldives are built on naturally shifting sand islands, so the concretion of the foundations of islands works against nature's natural change of island development (Kothari and Arnall, 2020). The development of hard 'sea walls' and other concrete structures around islands only borrows time away from natural erosion and movement.

Employing policies and actions at national and local levels for the good of citizens, within environmental limits, has been theoretically detailed by Raworth (2018), and is being employed by some cities now (e.g. Amsterdam). These models that only allow investment in projects that benefit the environment and people are very much needed at this critical time of diminished natural resource base. Recent resort developments in the Maldives, permitted under previous Maldivian governments, have not considered the on-costs of developments (e.g. social, coral reef degradation, fish habitat and waste treatment costs) to the

¹⁰ <https://www.tourism.gov.mv/dms/document/f5f522de183dde8f0f012884cecb1706.pdf>

¹¹ <https://tourism.gov.mv/en/registered/facilities/filter-t1>

¹² <https://www.dropbox.com/s/0b64j69s76et3r8/Summary%20-%20bottom-contact%20fishing%20MPA%20report%20%281%29.pdf?dl=0>

¹³ <https://www.gresham.ac.uk/watch-now/series/natural-capital>

¹⁴ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-south-asia-40827633>

environment in planning and remedial works. As a result of over-exploitation, development, and climate change impacts, the Maldivian environment is now less able to deliver local food (fish), coastal protection, homes, and a clean environment to its people. Infrastructure, such as capital investment in waste treatment, reef habitat protection, or creation and fish population enhancement tools, are needed to 'buffer' resort or other commercial development.

Prior to the 1990s, before mass-tourism developed in the Maldives, a healthy marine environment offered future generations long-term security. Citizens are now most concerned about housing, food, and security. Centralisation of decision-making by the Male' based governments, and poor decision-making, have previously resulted in the rejection of proposed conservation measures by local islands in North Ari (Grimsditch, personal communication). A June 2018 article interviewed the ex-environment minister in office (Mohamed Aslam; minister up to 2009) about the attitudes of the Maldivian public regarding environmental issues¹⁵. In the article, he implied there was no need for the two major political parties to consider environmental issues in their election campaigns, as these were not vote-winning issues. This was despite the designation of three very small MPAs prior to the 2018 election.

Reversing the trend

Before 2008, the Maldives lacked a champion for the protection and recovery of marine resources. However, the Maldives government of Nasheed once made very well intended statements to reverse this trend. In June 2012 Dr Mariyam Shakeela, the (then) Minister for Environment and Energy, announced a programme of work between 2013 and 2017 to achieve UNESCO Biosphere Reserve status for the entire nation. According to this plan, at least half the atolls of the nation were to implement marine conservation efforts like that of Baa atoll, which had UNESCO status. Despite the progressive political intentions of such statements, there was no strategy forthcoming from government agencies, such as the EPA or MRC, to designate or manage these sites. Similar promises by the UK government to designate a world-class network of MPAs have been met with meagre budgets for enacting and enforcing subsequent controls on fishing vessels. The trend is global, not national, for many policies not to be followed through with effective action at a national scale.

Regular monitoring of sites informing the international community of the health status of Maldives reefs has predominantly been undertaken by outside agencies (IUCN, local NGOs, international scientists, Reef Check, Biosphere Expeditions), until bleaching events occur. Many Maldives citizens have strong scepticism towards western conservation work. This is likely a result of Western tourists being tainted with the colonial brush as well as 'foreign' conservation efforts being considered alongside unsustainable foreign investment at odds with the cultural norms (e.g. de Vos, 2020). Biosphere Expeditions can continue to monitor reefs, but without enforcement, boats, trained officers, surveillance of vessels, and a judiciary that fines those that fish in MPAs and damage the coral reefs, there will be little support for conservation from the wider population (Zubair et al. 2011). Only after

¹⁵ <https://magazin.zenith.me/de/politik/mohamed-aslam-%C3%BCber-klimawandel-extremismus-und-politik-auf-den-malediven> (published online in 'Zenith', June 18, 2018)

investments are made in coral reef protection, fisheries restrictions, and water and waste treatment, will conservation start to deliver for people.

We believe that an entirely different approach is needed to manage the Maldives: a system whereby power is granted to atoll councils with a need to sustain local economies and growth, all within environmental limits. This will also result in well-being and security for local islands and populations, with funding available for local infrastructure moved away from private to public areas (e.g. better housing, schools, shoreline protection, MPA and fisheries enforcement).

Clearly the environmental assets that allow income for foreign markets do not 'feed the nation' but do provide large incomes for a few within the political and business elite. The UK and many western economies have also seen recent wealth gaps between the richest and poorest, with associated declines in the state of society¹⁶.

The Maldives is a 'canary in the coal mine' for global environmental degradation and the results of unbalanced power structures¹⁷. The concerning situation of the past can improve, but only if the current administration delivers a greater proportion of the profits (largely from tourism) into public services and proper environmental protection. The Maldives government has the power to make the 'paradise effect' of the Maldives help to pay for its recovery.

Conclusions

So how do we explain the multifarious factors that affect the current condition we see on the reefs of the Maldives? It is hard to tell what is going on from a few isolated sites, but the general trend is that the inner reefs have been impacted – particularly in North Ari and North Male' atolls.

First of all, our conclusions and solutions are the same as in previous reports, as there is little concerted top-down effort to deal with on-the-ground solutions to building environmental resilience in the Maldives.

Our conclusions come from long-term observations of these sites – Dega Thila, for example, was first visited in 2005 and surveyed in 2008. Concerns arise from the pointed decrease in corals at these sights; even in MPAs such as Rasdhoo Madivaru. This sight used to have a resident large population of red snapper and trevally, however they have now been absent from survey dives since 2018. Dega giri in western central Ari atoll is now almost totally dominated by corallimorphs, whilst Banyan Tree and Baros in North Male' atoll are being colonised by forms of encrusting sponges that grow close to the substrate. The Farish Faru reef in the west of Vaavu atoll (from 2019 and 2022 surveys) has fleshy lobed sponges that are in direct competition with hard corals – potentially another phase shift.

The outer reefs, in shallow water in particular, appear to be very similar in almost all locations, particularly where the drop-off is more extreme. Dhigurah, Rasdhoo Madivaru,

¹⁶ <https://theconversation.com/dont-listen-to-the-rich-inequality-is-bad-for-everyone-81952>

¹⁷ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/justice-home-affairs/opinion/unbalanced-politics-leads-to-unchecked-power/>

and Dhigurah Wall all resemble one another, have similar coral, coral rock, sponge, and algal counts.

After a decade of annual Reef Check surveys, we posit that there are broadly two different types of reef:

1. **Exposed outer (oceanic) reefs** are associated with greater currents, wave action, and are adjacent to very deep water. These areas are generally more resilient to bleaching because of the dominance of greater bleaching-resistant coral lifeforms and the cooler, deeper adjacent seawater (Cowburn et al. 2019).
2. **Inner reefs** are dominated by temperature-intolerant species such as branching *Acropora* and *Pocillopora*, which are subsequently more vulnerable to disease, *Drupella* predation, Crown of Thorns grazing, and sponge/algal recruitment and growth. In the central atolls of the Maldives, inner reefs are dominated by coral rock and turf algae. They may still be able to recruit corals and grow back to being coral dominated (e.g. Kudafalhu in central Ari), compared to those that have recruited toxic species such as *Discosoma* corallimorphs that appear to have few predators. It would seem from the literature that there may be a 'resort' affect, with lower recovery trajectories after bleaching being observed at inhabited reefs – but this is highly variable (e.g. Montefalcone et al. 2020).

We observe the following status of the reefs:

- A. In general, outer reefs that are exposed to colder oceanic waters appear to be more resilient than inner reefs that suffer more heat, pollution, fishing and nutrient stress.
- B. Some inner reefs are exhibiting a phase change from a coral-dominated state to an algal, sponge and *Discosoma* (non-coral) state (e.g. Dega Thila).
- C. Some inner (S Male' atoll) reefs have adapted to climate-induced bleaching with more bleaching- and sediment-tolerant coral species, e.g. *P. cylindrica* and *P. rus* persisting or outcompeting *Acropora* recruits, sponge, algae, and other competitors (e.g. southern Baros, Guraidhoo backreef and Beybe's).
- D. Certain reefs show some resistance to bleaching impacts, supporting species that were hitherto described as having low thermal tolerance (e.g. Farish faru in Vaavu) with large thickets of *Acropora* corals in deeper (>15m) water. The greater shelter and deeper nature of the colonies may have released these colonies from shallow water extreme SSTs during bleaching (waters under 5m). Note that this is the rarest form of reef we observed in our surveys since the 2016 bleaching event.

Our recommendations on issues related to coral reef vulnerability have been highlighted in previous reports available from the Biosphere Expeditions page on [ResearchGate](#). Our observations and training will hopefully increase awareness. Research has shown that recovery projections from bleaching events become more protracted over time, whilst more frequent bleaching events occur. Therefore, the Maldives will need decades to recruit and grow corals to resemble the reefs before the 1998 bleaching event. However, with the 2024

bleaching event occurring just four years after the last event, the ability to be resilient to such events is being tested more than ever before. As such, it is likely that the reefs will never regenerate to the levels seen in 1997 and before, and indeed, the species guilds – of corals at the very least – will be very different, particularly for inner atoll reefs.

Our recommendations are:

1. Invite either the EPA, or each atoll council, environmental officers to be present (with an office, officials, and boats) on each island atoll to control unsustainable fishing, dredging, and construction. Re-visiting the de-centralisation act would help facilitate local protection.
2. Fund sufficient EPA officers and atoll council law courts and enforcement officers to arrest and fine people who break environmental rules/laws in MPAs and at island house reefs. A Protected Areas Act with a duty to monitor and enforce could enable progress in this area.
3. Give the EPA funding to investigate & prosecute (fine) tourism or other developments where environmental damage is being caused (such as sediment outflows on live healthy reefs) above levels stated in Environment Impact Assessments. Enable EPA to do its job properly by divesting funds from developers to enforcers such that they have the staff and materials to effectively enforce their duties.
4. EPA officials must have knowledge of pristine (or semi-pristine) environmental baseline conditions to assess the relative scale of impact. They need funding to visit pristine reefs in remote parts of the archipelago to support them.
5. Ensure that fisheries department officials work collaboratively with the EPA in assessing fisheries' activities at resorts, grouper cages¹⁸, processing facilities, and at airports.
6. Ensure that every resort has to enact reef enhancement programmes that are not solely based on the construction of reef walls, but enable the development and growth of reef pyramids and fore-reef coral structures to allow sustainable growth under the water of a living wave barrier. Ensure advice from the MRC scientists and engineers is used to guide these efforts.
7. Introduce size limits on grouper fisheries as previously recommended to government (Wood et al., 2011), which include:
 - a. regulated fishing.
 - b. mandatory logbooks and data collection.
 - c. long-term monitoring of catch, abundance, and spawning aggregation sites.
 - d. national level awareness-raising programme.

¹⁸ Grouper cages exist in at least five atolls where fish are corralled before being shipped to Asian 'live fish' markets.

- e. a mobile-phone technology Vessel Monitoring Scheme (VMS) for Maldives-registered fishing vessels such that enforcement can be done by using satellite technology¹⁹.
8. Ensure that the fisheries department have enforcement officers based at fish cages to ensure that grouper size limits are met.
9. Ensure that EPA and fisheries department officers are stationed at or near to protected grouper spawning areas (see Figure 2.4a).
10. Ensure that the EPA is provided enough budget (via, for example, a tourism tax) to enable it to be present (with an officer) on tourist islands and enforce law and, if necessary, prosecute.
11. Ensure that the MRC is enabled, through an environment tax, to undertake rapid reef health assessment monitoring at all Maldivian resorts as a matter of law, and that the reports from the standard monitoring assessment are annually reported to government and made public.
12. Ensure all enforcement, fines, and prosecutions under the powers of the EPA and fisheries department are vetted by an independent body of accountants, lawyers, and governance experts, including officials, managers, and scientists from the EPA, MRC, and fisheries department of the Maldives.

¹⁹ Global Fishing Watch is used by Governments to assess illegal fishing activities in real time:
<https://globalfishingwatch.org/>

THE 5 SITES PROTECTED UNDER THE MALDIVES GROUPEL FISHERY MANAGEMENT PLAN

Figure 2.4a. Protected spawning areas that have bans on fishing in five atolls, as agreed by law after consultation with industry and government in 2011, but with little implementation of monitoring or regulation (from Wood et al, 2011).

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